

EPI-FLUORESCENT MICROSCOPY OF EDGE TRIMMED CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER: AN ALTERNATIVE TO CT-SCANNING

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ABSTRACT

X-ray computed tomography (XCT) can be used to detect edge milled carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) defects. Significantly this method is able to show sub-surface defects that cannot be captured by traditional methods such as stylus based or more novel areal methods of surface quality measurement. Whilst useful, this method can be prohibitive due to high equipment cost, scanning time and image resolution. XCT can often produce artefacts which falsely predict damage or obscure damage and depending on machine x-ray power often cannot resolve damage to fibre diameter which is critical when observing milled quality of the surface/sub-surface. This study utilises epi-fluorescent optical microscopy to provide high quality optical images as an alternative to XCT to observe through-depth damage of CFRP materials. The method of computing the novel damage criteria is presented as well as the validation of the method which compares the optical method to XCT images. Sub-surface damage of fabric and uni-directional materials in 0, 45, 90 and -45° orientations to the cutting edge is observed to demonstrate typical defects. A novel metric resulting from optical epi-fluorescent method provides a total area of damage when compared to a theoretically straight cut across the face of the edge milled CFRP. The method shows that different sub-surface damage exists for different fibre orientations to the cutting edge. In addition the method is shown to be a suitable alternative to XCT with scope for further development for industrial aerospace and automotive quality control of machined CFRP parts.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) manufacturing processes typically require an edge trimming process to achieve the final part shape [1, 2]. Edge milling is a subtractive method of achieving this net shape by removal of discrete chips of material. The cutting mechanisms involved in edge milling generate defects are specific to CFRP [3] and as such observing the quality of the surface is of vital importance as mechanical performance of the trimmed part may be reduced [4]. Historically

a stylus has been used to measure the surface quality of the trimmed edge with a focus on surface roughness (e.g. R_a) [5]. More recently areal measurement methods such as focus variation have been used to gather more information from the machined surface (e.g. S_a) [6].

Whilst improvements have been made to characterise the surface of the machined part quality, the full extent of damage may not be captured. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) has confirmed that matrix smearing during edge trimming operations can occur and occurs most predominantly in fibres oriented at 90° to the cutting edge [7] (image obtained from fabric machining noted in Section 2). Smearing occurs across the surface of edge trimmed samples due to high cutting temperatures generated through the abrasive nature of cutting. This temperature exceeds the glass transition (T_g) of the CFRP reinforcement material, where T_g is the state at which the polymer becomes rubbery before its melting point [8]. The trochoidal motion of the tool during milling smears the rubbery polymer across the surface, potentially hiding defects. An example of this smearing is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Smear matrix observed on the trimmed surface by SEM for fibres oriented at 90° to cutting edge

Recent work [9] has shown that XCT can be used to observe defects caused by the machining process. This method relies on the production of x-rays which penetrate the CFRP surface and are detected to produce 2D images. These images can be stitched together to provide a surface topography image of the machined material. Whilst the work of Nguyen-Dinh *et al.* [9] has been completed to observe effects which are traditionally shown through focus variation methods such as depth of crater damage, the CT method can also be used more effectively to observe machining defects which would not otherwise be seen, i.e. through-depth damage. However, the high costs of CT scanning equipment, high power consumption and long scan times to achieve useful resolutions can make this method prohibitive in addition to the XCT method not resolving defects to fibre diameter which potentially misses through-depth defects.

Therefore an alternative to measuring sub-surface XCT machining damage through use of epifluorescent (EF) optical microscopy designed specifically for edge trimming operations. The new method is then used to present a novel metric beyond current stylus and areal metrics in order to quantify damage which occurs at the surface and penetrates into the depth of the trimmed material. The method is then validated against XCT of the same trimmed edges.

2 PROPOSED METHOD

The proposed alternative to XCT requires through-depth observation of the edge trimmed material as shown in Figure 2 a). Samples are trimmed in order to fit in a 30 mm mounting cup using a water cooled Erbauer tile saw with a 1.6 mm thick diamond disc cutter.

Following sectioning the samples are mounted in Epo-fix which was mixed with Epo-dye (Struers, UK), an epoxy resin infused with fluorescent dye as shown in Figure 2 b). EF material has been used due to its ability to clearly show defects in damaged CFRP materials by providing extremely high contrast [10]. Cold mounting ensures that the damage caused by milling is not removed by heat which could potentially damage the CFRP material and change the specimen from its original machined condition. The mounted samples are placed in a vacuum of 0.1 N/mm^2 for 5 minutes to ensure that the resin penetrates any cracks present in the CFRP. The samples are then cured for 24 hrs at room temperature. Samples were abrasively polished to remove the face of the material which may have been damaged by the Erbauer tile saw and finally polished to provide a smooth surface for optical observation using the polishing regime noted in Ashworth *et. al.* [11].

Figure 2 – a) area of epi-fluorescent inspection of edge trimmed CFRP coupon and b) CFRP sample mounted in fluorescent resin

An Excelitas X-Cite ultra-violet light box, a 5MP Pax-it digital camera and microscope at 2 x magnification were used to capture the EF sample as shown in Figure 3 a).

The EF material has allowed a high contrast between damaged and un-damaged CFRP. In order to determine the amount of damage shown in Figure 3, the digital image can be subject to pixel thresholding. Thresholding of colour images is possible however the image was changed to a greyscale for simplicity of Matlab processing. A Matlab script changes the colour image to a greyscale image Figure 3 b).

A further Matlab sub-routine allows the user to define a straight edge which can be drawn across the edge of the image to represent a theoretical straight cutting line. Deviations from this cutting line are highlighted by the EF mounting material and thus represent damage. Automated Otsu thresholding [12] is then used within Matlab to yield a binary image of damaged areas as seen in Figure 3 c). Further Matlab calculations provide a novel damage metric which presents a pixel count/actual area (when used with a calibrated microscope) of machining induced damage in addition to a visual representation of damage.

Automated thresholding is chosen to remove potential user errors when selecting the threshold between bright and dark/ damaged and non-damaged areas. Whilst there is a clear difference by visual observation of the image, a histogram of the image pixels shows the majority of pixels grouped into light and dark areas however, some pixels are between bright and dark areas so a consistent, non-biased approach to threshold selection can be taken by using the Otsu method.

Figure 3 - a) epi-fluorescent image showing through depth damage, b) Matlab processed greyscale image and c) Matlab/Otsu processed binary image showing damage

3 VERIFICATION OF METHOD

In order to ensure that the proposed method observes defects due to machining and not due to the trimming of samples to fit into a mounting cup noted in Section 2, XCT scans of CFRP at differing fibre orientations to the cutting edge have been observed. In addition to observing defects of UD materials at fibre orientations of 0, 90, +45, -45° to the cutting edge, an observation of a fabric material has been completed. This array of fibre orientations to the cutting edge will not only allow verification of the EF method against XCT but also showcase typical defects that occur due to the edge trimming process.

UD laminates were manufactured from twelve layers of MTM46-36%-12KHTS40-250-300 (Solvay, UK), a high performance toughened epoxy resin pre-preg, in order to create a specimen of 3

mm thickness. The laminate was cured using an autoclave regime shown in Table 1. The $[(0,90)/(+45,-45)]_3/(0,90)$ fabric material was manufactured using an RTM process described in Ashworth *et. al.* [7] to create a 3 mm thick cured laminate.

Table 1 – MTM46 curing regime

Segment	Temperature target	Temperature ramp rate	Pressure (bar)	Pressure Ramp rate (bar/min)	Dwell time (mins)
1	120	2	6.2	0.2	60
2	180	2	6.2	-	60
3	20	3	0	0.5	-

All materials have been edge trimmed using a full slot up/conventional milling procedure with a diamond coated burr style tool (OSG Corporation, UK). The DIA-BNC tool is a fine nicked router designed for CFRP trimming with the nick and flute form designed to eliminate uncut fibres and delamination. The DIA-BNC tool has a double helix, each at 15° with a relief and rake angle of 18° and 8° , respectively. The machining parameters used for all trimming operations are given in Table 2. The same tool was used for all trials.

Table 2 – Machining parameters

Tool	No. teeth	Tool diameter (mm)	Cutting speed (m/min)	Feed per tooth (mm/tooth)	Feed per revolution (mm/rev)
DIA-BNC	8	6	179	0.015	0.12

Fabric and UD material was machined using a MAG Cincinnati CFV and XYZ 1060HS VMC 3-axis milling machine respectively. Samples were rigidly clamped to custom tooling blocks which allowed an unsupported edge with an overhang of 0.5mm to allow the milling tool to engage with CFRP material with a single pass. Machining was completed without coolant and a Karcher 001 NT 35/1 Tact Te H extraction system was used to capture harmful CFRP dust [13] at source.

UD samples at $+45^\circ$, 90° and -45° orientation contained uncut burrs which is typical of the machining process [14]. These burrs were removed prior to XCT as the fibres caused artefacts in test scans due to image lag and ghosting [15].

XCT was completed using Skyscan 1172 equipment with following settings;

- Voltage: 40 kV
- Current: 149 μ A
- Filter: none; the low power nature of the machine necessitates the use of all emitted X-rays
- Exposure level = 295

Post-processing of the images was completed using CTvox, a free to download software with limited functionality to produce images such as those shown in Figure 4. The 3D image is made of up to 1,879 single planar slice .tiff images which can be used for direct comparison to EF images such as that shown in Figure 3 a). As such, each image is separated by approximately 8.75 μ m. Comparison of individual XCT .tiff images will be made with a single EF image to observe if the machined edge damage is replicated. It is noted that the final image resolution, artefacts and approximate distance between images may cause errors in exact visual comparison to EF images.

Figure 4 – 3D XCT scan of UD fibres oriented at 0° to the cutting edge made from 1879 planar .tiff images to allow comparison to EF method

4 RESULTS

Figure 5 shows the binary images created through use of the novel damage metric for the various fibre orientations used within this study. By applying the thresholding method described in Section 2, the total amount of damage compared to a theoretically straight cut can be calculated. The amount of damage is shown in in Figure 6.

It can be seen that machining 90° fibres forms the greatest level of damage. Figure 5 shows large scale damage along the length of the fibres/fibre-matrix interface. The damage occurring during machining of 90° is as described in Wang *et. al.* [16] with the cutting force causing shear of the fibres with the force also causing a mode I type opening along the fibre-matrix interface. Fibres at +45° to the cutting edge exhibit the least amount of damage when using the novel metric even compared to 0° fibres which typically exhibit the least amount of surface damage according to literature [3]. However, the sub-surface damage of the 0° fibre specimen may have occurred due to a void in the laminate which has been exposed by the machining process. -45° fibres typically exhibit the most amount of surface damage due to the fracture below the cutting plane [3] however results show a low amount of sub-surface damage compared to 0 and +45° samples. It is noted that the measurements of damage provided by Sheikh-Ahmad [3] and Wang *et. al.* [16] refer to surface damage and not sub-surface damage. This may account for the differences observed and highlights the importance of measuring sub-surface defects which would otherwise not be seen. The fabric material shows the second highest level of sub-surface damage and when compared to 0, +45 and -45° fibres, the trimmed edge is not as straight. This may be a difference due to machine stability which is known to change the properties of the machined surface [7] or it may be due to the individual ply orientations being supported at either side by differing fibre orientations. This may change the chip formation method and subsequent sub-surface/surface damage. It is also noted that the fabric material uses 3k fibre tows whilst the UD material is made from 12k fibre tows which may change the fracture mode causing differing levels of damage.

Figure 5 shows that sub-surface defects have occurred for fabric, 0° and 90° fibres which would not have been captured with methods such as focus variation. Whilst images show sub-surface damage, it is noted that a larger population of sectioned material is required to draw full conclusions of cutting modes of differing fibre orientations.

Figure 5 – Binary images denoting damage obtained through novel metric calculations

Figure 6 – Novel metric damage results for differing fibre orientations to the cutting edge

Figure 7 - Verification of epi-fluorescent method by comparison with single planar slice XCT

Figure 7 shows the verification results when the EF method is compared to XCT images. Whilst the resolution of the XCT is limited by relatively high distance between scan sections compared to fibre diameter, artefacts and ghosting, all of which do not allow individual fibres to be imaged, it can be seen that major areas of damage on the machined edge seen through XCT is replicated in the EF images. Importantly the EF images do not exhibit further damage from the processing method. The machined edge shown for the -45° XCT sample does not match the EF closely which may be due to the distance between individual images taken by the XCT equipment however the contrast available shows some light greyscale areas which can be interpreted to allow a match with the EF image.

Visible transverse cracks for 90° fibres can be seen in the EF image in Figure 7 and are observed to a less visible extent in the XCT image. This is due to power limitations in the XCT equipment which does not allow resolution to individual fibre level in addition to the production of artefacts which mask areas of no material.

Low damage has been exhibited for fibres at $+45^\circ$ to the cutting edge due to the clean shearing mechanism of the fibres. Therefore it is difficult to verify the EF method with the resolution limit of the XCT equipment used. However Figure 8 shows validation through inspection of a deeper surface which shows that voids are seen alongside a small amount of edge damage which can be seen in the XCT image.

Figure 8 – Further verification of damage to $+45^\circ$ fibres

5 CONCLUSIONS

This investigation assessed the sub-surface, machining induced damage of fabric and UD, edge milled CFRP by using an EF method and a novel damage criteria. Further to this the EF method was verified by XCT. Based on the experimental results obtained, the following conclusions can be drawn;

- The bulk damage due to the cutting edge is the same between XCT and EF images. This suggests that EF is a suitable alternative to the XCT method.
- The EF method presented is able to identify areas of sub-surface damage which would not be visible to surface analysis techniques such as stylus or focus variation microscopy. Further to this the method is able to more accurately measure subsurface damage than the XCT method.
- By using the EF method, a novel metric which accounts for machining induced damage of CFRP edge trimming has been generated. The novel metric is able to provide a value for total damage area compared to a theoretically straight cut.
- Fibres at different orientations to the cutting edge exhibit different sub-surface damage levels.
- The sub-surface damage observed by the limited sample size shows that sub-surface damage may differ to the typical surface damage mechanisms shown in current literature.

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